

13C-based MFA: flux estimates

Table 1: Overview of estimated (free) net and exchange fluxes and associated confidence intervals for the CelA-producing strain and the empty-plasmid strain based on repeated 13C-experiments.

	<i>S. lividans</i> pIJ486		<i>S. lividans</i> pIJ486-CelA	
G6P → F6P	46.89	(42.28, 54.57)	23.78	(19.44, 32.64)
PEP → PYR	107.94	(103.24, 111.75)	129.04	(126.23, 132.40)
CO ₂ dilution flux	8.99	(5.83, 12.81)	0.00	(0.00, 4.50)
ACE secretion	31.51	(22.51, 39.43)	34.31	(26.70, 43.89)
AKG secretion	0.11	(0.09, 0.13)	0.36	(0.29, 0.42)
PYR secretion	1.55	(1.09, 1.99)	9.84	(9.32, 10.45)
ALA → Biomass	3.16	(2.99, 3.32)	2.08	(1.98, 2.22)
ALA → CelA	-		0.02	(0.01, 0.03)
ALA → Protein	0.08	(0.06, 0.09)	0.09	(0.07, 0.11)
1-GLC uptake	44.01	(43.79, 44.20)	44.03	(43.84, 44.20)
U-GLC uptake	55.56	(55.44, 55.70)	55.63	(55.50, 55.77)
PEP + CO ₂ ↔ OAA	20.72	(15.01, 29.31)	38.43	(32.13, 44.01)
G6P ↔ F6P	>1000	(353.13, ∞)	>1000	(528.62, ∞)
FBP ↔ 2 GAP	>1000	(0.00, 131.68)	>1000	(0.00, 53.17)
GAP ↔ PGA	>1000	(0.00, ∞)	>1000	(0.00, ∞)
PGA ↔ PEP	>1000	(708.42, ∞)	>1000	(1645.78, ∞)
2 R5P ↔ S7P + GAP	30.84	(4.41, 50.76)	48.13	(21.58, 90.53)
R5P + E4P ↔ GAP + F6P	20.83	(13.99, 28.08)	4.29	(0.00, 11.51)
GAP + S7P ↔ E4P + F6P	30.20	(22.49, 63.77)	8.87	(0.00, 44.77)
PYR ↔ AcCoA + CO ₂	9.42	(5.51, 12.46)	0.26	(0.00, 2.73)
AKG ↔ SUCC + CO ₂	0.00	(0.00, 6.07)	1.99	(0.00, 12.06)
SUCC ↔ FUM	>1000	(0.00, ∞)	>1000	(0.00, ∞)
FUM ↔ MAL	>1000	(57.35, ∞)	>1000	(55.36, ∞)
MAL ↔ OAA	127.96	(119.84, ∞)	130.73	(124.55, ∞)

Table 2: Overview of all estimated net fluxes and their confidence interval in the central carbon metabolism of CelA-producing *S. lividans* and the empty plasmid reference strain. Both absolute flux values and normalised values are given. Estimated fluxes of biomass and protein are expressed in gram and milligram, respectively.

Fluxes	CelA strain		Reference strain		CelA strain Absolute flux values (mmol/gDW.h)	Reference strain Absolute flux values (mmol/gDW.h)
	Normalised (mmol/100 mmol glucose)	Reference strain	Reference strain	Reference strain		
<i>Free fluxes</i>						
coIn	0.00 (0:4.50)	8.99 (5.83:12.81)			0.00 (0:0.09)	0.22 (0.14:0.31)
Eff_Ac	34.31 (26.7:43.89)	31.51 (22.51:39.43)			0.68 (0.53:0.87)	0.76 (0.54:0.95)
Eff_AKG	0.36 (0.29:0.42)	0.11 (0.09:0.13)			0.01 (0.01:0.01)	0 (0:0)
Eff_PYR	9.84 (9.32:10.45)	1.55 (1.09:1.99)			0.19 (0.18:0.21)	0.04 (0.03:0.05)
emp1	23.78 (19.44:32.64)	46.89 (42.28:54.57)			0.47 (0.38:0.65)	1.13 (1.02:1.32)
emp6	129.04 (126.23:132.4)	107.94 (103.24:111.75)			2.55 (2.5:2.62)	2.61 (2.49:2.7)
Biomass efflux	5.72 (5.45:6.11)	8.67 (8.22:9.13)			0.11 (0.11:0.12)	0.21 (0.2:0.22)
CelA secretion	18.53 (9.27:27.8)				0.37 (0.18:0.55)	
Protein secretion	104.33 (81.15:127.51)	86.10 (71.58:99.74)			2.07 (1.61:2.52)	2.08 (1.73:2.41)
<i>Dependent fluxes</i>						
ana1	0.03 (0:2.48)	6.58 (4.1:9.84)			0.00 (0:0.05)	0.16 (0.1:0.24)
ana3	15.25 (14.57:17.69)	28.82 (26.17:32.05)			0.30 (0.29:0.35)	0.7 (0.63:0.77)
coExch	0.00 (0:5.67)	8.99 (5.83:12.81)			0.00 (0:0.11)	0.22 (0.14:0.31)
coOut	283.04 (261.48:296.53)	206.94 (194.83:220.71)			5.60 (5.18:5.87)	5 (4.7:5.33)
emp2	67.97 (66.46:71.29)	72.31 (70.94:74.66)			1.95 (1.32:1.41)	1.75 (1.71:1.8)
emp3	67.97 (66.46:71.29)	72.31 (70.94:74.66)			1.35 (1.32:1.41)	1.75 (1.71:1.8)
emp4	155.23 (153.31:158.83)	153.09 (151.3:155.89)			3.07 (3.04:3.14)	3.7 (3.65:3.76)
emp5	148.14 (145.88:151.91)	142.45 (140.36:145.49)			2.93 (2.89:3.01)	3.44 (3.39:3.51)
ppp1	75.27 (65.95:80.13)	51.66 (44:56.35)			1.49 (1.31:1.59)	1.25 (1.06:1.36)
ppp4	23.94 (20.88:25.58)	15.47 (12.93:17.12)			0.47 (0.41:0.51)	0.37 (0.31:0.41)
ppp5	22.22 (19.23:23.89)	12.93 (10.44:14.59)			0.44 (0.38:0.47)	0.31 (0.25:0.35)
ppp6	23.94 (20.88:25.58)	15.47 (12.93:17.12)			0.47 (0.41:0.51)	0.37 (0.31:0.41)
tea1	103.98 (99.54:108.59)	90.30 (85.7:94.98)			2.06 (1.97:2.15)	2.18 (2.07:2.29)
tea2	58.03 (50.13:63.56)	41.22 (37.24:47.51)			1.15 (0.99:1.26)	1 (0.9:1.15)
tea3	58.03 (50.13:63.56)	41.22 (37.24:47.51)			1.15 (0.99:1.26)	1 (0.9:1.15)
tea4	52.51 (44.7:57.8)	33.43 (29.33:39.64)			1.04 (0.89:1.14)	0.81 (0.71:0.96)
tea6	52.51 (44.7:57.8)	33.43 (29.33:39.64)			1.04 (0.89:1.14)	0.81 (0.71:0.96)
tea7a	26.25 (22.35:28.9)	16.72 (14.67:19.82)			0.52 (0.44:0.57)	0.4 (0.35:0.48)
tea7b	26.25 (22.35:28.9)	16.72 (14.67:19.82)			0.52 (0.44:0.57)	0.4 (0.35:0.48)
tea8	52.47 (44.07:57.76)	26.86 (21.86:31.61)			1.04 (0.87:1.14)	0.65 (0.53:0.76)